

WHAT IS A WEB-QUEST?

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ANNOTATION

This article examines the effectiveness of using webquest technology as a way to implement project activities in English lessons. The concept of a webquest is considered.

Key words: *web quest (web-quest), Internet resources, project activities, information technology*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматривается эффективность использования технологии веб-квестов как способа реализации проектной деятельности на уроках английского языка. Рассмотрено понятие веб-квеста.

Ключевые слова: *веб-квест (веб-квест), интернет-ресурсы, проектная деятельность, информационные технологии.*

WEB-QUEST TEXNOLOGIYASI NIMA?

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola ingliz tili darslarida loyiha faoliyatini amalga oshirish usuli sifatida web-quest texnologiyasidan foydalanish samaradorligini ko'rib chiqadi. Veb-kvest tushunchasi ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlari: *web quest (web-quest), Internet resources, project activities, information technology.*

INTRODUCTION

Web-quest structure

- topic selection
- selection of internet service and design
- selection of tasks, web resources, planned results
- filling the webquest with content

A webquest in pedagogy is a problematic task with elements of a role-playing game, for the implementation of which information resources of the Internet are used.

This means that the teacher, when composing assignments, selects information on the Internet where the necessary materials can be found, giving students the appropriate hyperlinks [1]. All this is stored on some web resource, designed and structured as a web quest. Students in groups or individually complete the proposed web-quest tasks, upon completion of which they present their own web pages on a given topic, or some other creative work in electronic, printed or oral form.

Actively developing information technologies are important for the formation of an integral system of universal knowledge, skills and abilities.

Currently, students are fluent in information and communication technologies, using them in their daily life and educational process. Student's worldview is closely connected with all kinds of gadgets and electronic devices. That is why, in order for the lesson to be as interesting and effective as possible, the teacher needs to use possible modern information technologies that provide not only clarity, but also active learning and student involvement in this process.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The term "Web-Quest" was first proposed in the summer of 1995 by Bernie Dodge, a professor of educational technology at the University of San Diego (USA). The author developed innovative Internet applications for integration into the educational process when teaching various academic subjects at different levels of education [1].

Kenton Letkeman, the creator of a number of excellent webquests, believes that this is a super learning tool, because... A constructivist approach to learning is used.

When completing webquests, students do not receive ready-made answers or solutions; they independently solve the task assigned to them [2].

Working on a webquest helps

- organize active independent or group search activities
- promotes the development of creative thinking and problem solving skills
- makes it possible to implement an individual approach
- trains thinking abilities (explanation, comparison, classification, highlighting general and specific)

Thus, we can say that the webquest technology is based on an activity-based approach.

Classification of webquests.

Web quests can cover either a separate problem, academic subject, topic, or be interdisciplinary; Bernie Dodge identifies three principles for classifying web quests:

1. By duration of implementation: short-term and long-term.
2. By subject content: mono-projects and interdisciplinary web quests.
3. By the type of tasks performed by students: retelling tasks, compilation tasks, mystery tasks, journalistic tasks, design tasks, creative product tasks, solving controversial problems (consensus building tasks), persuasion tasks, self-knowledge tasks, analytical tasks, judgment tasks, scientific tasks.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Retelling tasks are the most primitive and represent the simplest example of using the Internet as a source of information. There is even an opinion that webquests based only on retelling cannot be considered a webquest. However, in most cases, retelling is allowed as a task for a webquest, provided that:

- the format and form of student reports differs markedly from the original materials, that is, they are not simply copying text from the Internet into a text editor;

- students are free to choose what to talk about and how to organize the information they find;

- Students use skills of summarizing, selecting, and processing information.

Creative web quests (creative products task) require students to create a product in a given format (painting, play, poster, game, song, website, multimedia presentation, etc.). Creative projects are similar to design projects, but are freer and more unpredictable in their results. When evaluating such projects, greater emphasis should be placed on student creativity and self-expression [3].

Bernie Dodge highlights the clear structure of the webquest: Introduction, Task, Process, Evaluation, Conclusion, Credits, TeacherPage.

However, this structure is not something fixed and is used only as a basis, which can be changed if necessary. The teacher can design the quest in accordance with the level and needs of his students.

Introduction - a statement of the topic, a description of the main roles of the participants, a quest script, a work plan or an overview of the entire quest. The goal is to prepare and motivate students. Therefore, motivational and educational value are important here.

Task - a clear and interesting description of the problematic task and the form of presentation of the final result.

- a problem or riddle that needs to be solved;
- position that needs to be formulated and defended;
- the product to be created;
- the abstract to be created;
- report or journalistic account;
- creative work, presentation, poster, etc.;

The task must be problematic, clearly formulated, and have educational value.

Process (Execution) - an accurate description of the main stages of work; guidelines for action, useful tips for collecting information (checklist of questions for analyzing information, various tips for completing a particular task, “blank” Web

pages for reports, recommendations for using information resources, etc.); From a methodological point of view, the material should be distinguished by the relevance, diversity and originality of resources; variety of tasks, their focus on the development of high-level thinking skills; availability of methodological support - auxiliary and additional materials for completing tasks; when using elements of a role-playing game - an adequate selection of roles and resources for each role [4].

Here you can specify links to resources and not allocate a separate section for them.

Evaluation - a description of the criteria and parameters for evaluating the completion of a webquest, which is presented in the form of an evaluation form. Evaluation criteria depend on the type of educational tasks that are solved in the webquest.

The methodological assessment is subject to the adequacy of the presented assessment criteria to the type of task, the clarity of the description of the assessment criteria and parameters, and the ability to measure the results of the work.

Conclusion - a brief and accurate description of what students will learn by completing this webquest. There should be a connection here with the introduction.

Credits (Materials Used) - links to resources used to create the webquest. This section can be combined with the Process section.

TeacherPage (Comments for the teacher) - methodological recommendations for teachers who will use the webquest.

- origin, goals and objectives of the webquest, what it's about
- age category of students (can it be used by other students if there are additions, adjustments)
- planned results, based on learning standards (personal, regulatory, communicative, cognitive)
- the process of organizing a webquest
- necessary resources
- the value and dignity of this webquest

Webquests in language teaching

The use of web quests and other tasks based on Internet resources in language teaching requires students to have an appropriate level of language proficiency to work with authentic Internet resources. In this regard, the effective integration of web quests into the process of teaching foreign languages is possible in cases where the web quest: is a creative task that completes the study of a topic; accompanied by training lexical and grammatical exercises based on the language material of the authentic resources used in the webquest. Performing such exercises can either precede work on the quest, or be carried out in parallel with it.

CONCLUSION

A webquest, using Internet information resources and integrating them into the educational process, helps to effectively solve a number of practical problems, since in the process of working on a webquest a number of competencies are developed:

- use of information technologies to solve professional problems;
- self-learning and self-organization;
- team work;
- ability to find several ways to solve a problem situation.

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